

**ECONOMICS AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES:
NEW HORIZONS OF TEACHING**

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ABSTRACT

This thesis examines the use of information technologies in the teaching of economic sciences in the context of digitalization. New forms of learning such as online courses, simulations, and data analysis are analyzed. An increase in student engagement and the development of digital competencies are noted. Special attention is given to the importance of digitalization for universities in Uzbekistan.

The modern economy is inconceivable without information technologies, and the digitalization of education is becoming a necessary condition for training specialists capable of working in a knowledge-based economy [2, p. 16]. ICTs acquire particular importance in the teaching of economic disciplines, where they not only transform the pedagogical process but also directly shape the professional competencies of future economists.

One of the key directions of digitalization is the implementation of online learning and hybrid formats. Platforms such as Moodle [13], Coursera [6], and EdX [9] provide flexibility in education, automate testing processes, and promote students' independence [5]. The second direction involves the use of simulation programs and business games (Capsim [7], Marketplace Live [12]), which model real business processes and contribute to the development of managerial thinking [4]. The third direction is associated with the formation of data-handling skills: analytical tools such as Excel Power BI [10] and Google Data Studio [11] enable students to acquire competencies that are in demand in the labor market.

Studies conducted by the National Research University Higher School of Economics (HSE) show that the use of simulations and online courses increases student engagement by 35% [3], while the experience of the London School of Economics demonstrates a reduction in the gap between theory and practice when analyzing digital case studies [8].

Impact of ICT on the Teaching of Economic Disciplines

Area of ICT Application	Tools	Result
Online Learning	Moodle, Coursera, Zoom	Flexibility of learning, growth of student autonomy
Simulations and Business Games	Capsim, Marketplace Live	Development of managerial and analytical skills
Data Analysis	Python, R, Power BI	Formation of digital competencies
Virtual Research	Google Scholar, Scopus	Development of research skills

In Uzbekistan, the digitalization of higher education is institutionalized at the state level. The Ministry of Higher Education is implementing electronic libraries, distance learning systems (Moodle, Google Classroom, Ziyonet), and national digital resources [1]. Within the framework of teaching economics, this enables students to work with real statistical data from the State Committee on Statistics of the Republic of Uzbekistan and international databases of the World Bank. Universities across the country are introducing business games in financial management, which contribute to the development of decision-making skills under uncertainty.

Thus, digital technologies in the teaching of economic disciplines act not merely as an auxiliary tool, but as a strategic component of professional training. Their implementation enables a shift from the transmission of ready-made knowledge to the formation of research and analytical skills. In the future, further expansion of digitalization can be expected through the integration of artificial intelligence and virtual reality into the educational process.

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